

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers,

Welcome to the second regular issue in 2016. As always, I'd like to thank all institutions, reviewers and authors for their valuable support and work. Please consider yourself and encourage your colleagues to submit high-quality articles to our journal.

During this year, several of the long-standing members of our editorial board retired. First, I'd like to express my deep gratitude for their valuable support – in many cases over 22 years – and wish them all the best for the future. Second, I would like to use this opportunity to invite researchers from all areas of computer science to join our editorial board: if you are a tenured Associate Professor or above with a good publication record, please do apply for a membership in our editorial board. It would be great to have you with us!

Also, we encourage the submission of high-quality proposals of special issues which cover emerging topics and new trends in various fields of computer science. You can find detailed information about the publication of special issues at http://www.jucs.org/ujs/jucs/info/special_issues/special_guidelines.html.

In this regular issue, I am pleased to introduce 5 accepted papers from 6 different countries.

Unai Aguilera and Diego Lopez-de-Ipina from Spain propose MANET, a semantically enhanced discovery system which overcomes the lack of central manager nodes by the classification of service's parameters according to a shared domain ontology. In a collaborative research between Guatemala, Ecuador and Spain, Hector R. Amado-Salvatierra, José R. Hiler, Salvador Otón Tortosa, Rocael Hernández Rizzardini and Nelson Piedra propose a methodological framework to take into account accessibility in the different processes of the life cycle of virtual educational projects. Marat Faizrahmanov and Iskander Kalimullin from Russia report on their finding of enumeration spectrum hierarchy of α -families and low α degrees. Afshin Lamei and Mehran S. Fallah from Iran focus their research on rewriting mechanisms that allow tracking feature transparently in the dependence graphs. Last but not least, Giani Petri and Christiane Gresse von Wangenheim from Brazil present a literature review on how educational games can be evaluated.

As always, I thank all reviewers involved in the evaluation of the published article for their valuable support and acknowledge the efforts and help of all reviewers who reviewed articles that did not make it to publication.

Enjoy Reading!

Cordially,

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Christian Gütl', with a stylized flourish at the end.

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